

BUILDING SERVICES AND FACILITY MANAGEMENT IN HIGH RISE BUILDING

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ABSTRACT:

What is facility management? It is simply management of building and services. There are various building services provided in the high rise building such as plumbing, sanitation, water supply air conditioning and fire fighting. To make staying in high rise buildings comfortable, special aspects need to be considered. All the tall buildings should have requisite amenities and services that would be suitable to its nature. Therefore care and attention must be paid for satisfying the service requirements during general planning as well as structural planning of high rise buildings as they are very important. So it is very important to study the building services like plumbing, sanitation, ventilation, air conditioning, electrification.

INTRODUCTION:

Introduction to the building services and facilities in the high-rise residential buildings in order to make a comprehensive study of all the services and facilities for those involved in the construction field. The need of the hour is 'vertical expansion' and high-rise buildings can run successfully without the proper installation of the services. The idea of providing services and user services starts in the conceptual stage of design. One has to be acquainted with the service standards as per the design of the building. The prime aim should be Safety and Quality in the construction of high-rise buildings. The future insight with respect to the long life of the building must be targeted. The above objective has been achieved through the case-studies which have been done. It has been observed that in practice, on one hand some of the services are installed as per the norms but on the other hand there are a few areas which are neglected. It has been easy to study the subject through the live examples of the buildings. Here are some are conclusions which are drawn from the case studies.

METHODOLOGY:

How the study was conducted and the various steps taken from the beginning to the completion of the study. It starts with the setting of the study, then, the study population, sample frame, sample size and sampling technique adopted. Others include data collection instruments and methods of data analysis. The

investigation took place in seven villages located in the area known and referred to as the Pimpri Chinchwad municipal corporation zone of Pune. These are Akurdi, Pimple Gurav, Pimple Chinchwad, Pimpri Waghere, Tathawade, Ravet, Wakad villages. The population of the study consisted of all the high rise buildings within the PCMC, Pune identified above. High rise buildings are buildings having height more than 35 m. Such structures must have facilities such as twenty-four hours water supply, uninterrupted power supply. There are more than seven thousand buildings were permitted by PCMC, Pune among which One thousand and fifty-three high rise buildings were permitted which is a huge number to carry out the survey for the study. Another thing is that most of the high rise buildings permitted but is incomplete in completion status for various reasons. So for this study the focus is given on the buildings which are completed before 2012. In order to secure representative responses, the size of the sample of high rise building for the study should not fall below the representative size determined by statistical estimation theory, which is based on the degree of confidence that the researcher wishes to employ (Kothari, 1978). For this study, the researcher defines how large a sample of high rise building should be in order to be 95% confident that the probable error of using a sample rather than surveying the whole population will not exceed 0.02%. The following formula is given:

$$N = \frac{Z\alpha^2 n \beta (1 - \beta)}{(n - 1) \delta^2 + Z\alpha^2 \beta (1 - \beta)}$$

N will be maximum and the sample will yield at least the desired precision.

δ is the true value of β which in this case is 0.02 or 2%. In this case, the formula yields 09. So 9 No of buildings are selected for study.

One of the features of a good research design is the generation of data for refuting or validating the apriori expectations or hypotheses. Both primary and secondary data were generated for this research. Primary data mainly came from direct observation of the events, manipulation of variables, and contrivance of research situations including responses to questionnaires. Secondary data are also required for this research, which came from PCMC, Pune.

The research method adopted for this work to generate the required data was survey research. The survey research basically focused on self-administered questionnaires complemented with in-depth personal interview, physical survey of the constructed facilities, in-depth study of system operations and facilities bench marking

ANALYSIS OF DATA:

Comprehensive breakdown of data collected from questionnaires administered to tenants in seven villages in Pimpri Chinchwad Municipal Corporation of Pune.

The analysis undertaken in this has been arranged into two sections. The first section examines the preliminary survey details along with the profiles of the selected case studies and customers involved in the study. Finally, the second section is the summary and concluding remarks. For first section, exploratory data analysis (EDA) is first embarked upon prior to more rigorous statistical analysis in line with Tan (2004). However, it must be stated that some of the analysis or tables are preliminary or preamble to another which may warrant scanty comments. At the summary level for each variable, research question or objective, extensive discussions are made.

Data was collected between the months of April and November, 2016. The administration and retrieval was achieved personally and with the aid of a field assistant in each of the seven villages. The various responses were subsequently coded and analyzed between August 2016 and November 2016 by means of Microsoft Excel Spread Sheet Analysis.

Aggregated responses to the various building services of facilities management driven building occupant. The responses, when assembled and sorted, with principles of exclusiveness and exhaustiveness in mind, brought out the 4 traits as shown in their ranking. Adequate and functional facilities came first, followed by quality accommodation with competitive charges coming on the rear. These traits buttresses the findings earlier stated.

RESULT:

Respondents were asked total 25 questions regarding facilities to indicate the satisfaction level. These question are based on the various building services and facility management such as plumbing, sanitation, water supply, fire fighting, lift and elevator, parking and air conditioning. With the help of liker scale the results are interpreted. The liker scale used for work is shown in table

Very good	Good	Average	Satisfactory	Poor
5	4	3	2	1

The responses of every question are driver and arranged in descending order. The higher percentage of response shows the occupants are satisfied with service and lower percentage shows the occupants are not satisfied. At the time of study it found that respondents have recorded 'Poor' as satisfaction level to none of the questions.

CONCLUSION:

Following points are concluded from this paper:-

From case study it was found that the plumbing and sanitation services are give more wattage. Occupants are satisfied with plumbing and sanitation. In some of building it was found that the storage of water for breakdown condition is not given more importance

In the all case studies, the electrical work, the standard materials and workmanship has been followed as per the Indian Standards and compliance with the construction work. There is use of child safe switches, fire alarm, fire wires, motion sensor lights and earth leakage circuit breakers in all building. Consumers are fully satisfied with electrical services) to study the existing building services and facilities management in some selected high rise building as a case study.

In all case studies, adequate measure has been taken for fire-fighting. Hydrants are provided near the staircase and sprinkler system has been provided at the basement parking. In some of case study fire fighting storage tanks is not given much importance In all the buildings, there are minimum 2 lifts in each building but there is no provision of fire-lift. In some of building there is provision of visitor lift. At time of study it was found that costumers are satisfied with lift and elevator services.

At the time of case studies it is found that, the cleanliness of water tank and maintenance of drainage system not given much more importance. It creates problem to occupants. Hence, it is to be considered that the planning of building services should not be neglected in the conceptual stage in any high-rise building. If neglected in the initial stage, creates problems in the later stage of construction and would remain as a curse for the rest of the life of the building and the occupants.

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